

Effect of Discovery Method on Interest in Ecology Concept among Senior Secondary School Students in Zaria Metropolis, Kaduna State.

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Abstract

The study adopted a Quasi Experimental research design Specifically, pretest and posttest research design. The population of the study consists of 465 (Male,70 And Female,48) senior secondary school class two (SSII) Biology students during the 2023/2024 academic session among public schools in Zaria metropolis, Kaduna state, a sample size of 118 (70 male and 48 female) students were selected from the target population using multi-stage sampling technique. Two research questions and corresponding null hypotheses guided the study. Ecology Interest Questionnaire (EIQ) was validated by experts and reliability coefficients using Pearson product moment coefficient (PPMC) was found to be 0.76 using test-retest Method. Mean and standard deviation were used to answer the research questions, while independent T-test was used to test the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. The findings revealed that students exposed to discovery strategy have high interest scores than those students exposed to conventional method of teaching and the research also showed that female students have high interest scores than their male counterparts when exposed to discovery strategy of teaching. The study conclude that there is significant difference in the mean interest scores of the SSII students taught ecology concept using discovery method and those taught that same concept using conventional method of teaching in favour of experimental group. The study recommended that Biology teachers should use discovery strategy of teaching while teaching ecology so as to improve students' interest during the teaching and learning process.

Keywords: Discovery method, interest, ecology, students

Introduction

Discovery teaching strategies implies “induction”. By it, students proceed from specific example to concepts and from concepts to a generalization or principle. Mandrin and preckel (2009) further explains that we need not show learners everything; they can find out for themselves, even the non-literate learners, and an opportunity must always offer in to experiment and find out by themselves. He also stated that in discovery teaching learners find out by themselves via doing with their hands; the new knowledge acquired and understandings they need; they discover new ways of doing things, develop and acquire skills of their own. The learners watched carefully by the instructor, are active in their own learning.

Biology as related to science is a natural science that deals with the living world: How the world is structured, how it functions and what these functions are, how it develops, how living things came into existence, and how they react to one another and with their environment (Umar, 2011). Ecology is also one of the branches of Biology mentioned above and one of the important variables in this study. It's the studies living and non-living things and their environment. Ecology is a branch of biology defined as the study of the relationship of organism or group of organisms and their environment; or the science of the interrelationship among living organisms and their environment. The poor performance of candidates in the School Certificate Biology Examinations conducted by the West African Examination Council has also attributed to some topics in

Biology which students find difficult to answer correctly especially in the area of Ecology (Adebanjo, 2019). According to Renninger and Hidi, (2015) to better comprehend the role of interest in learning and understand how interest influences student success, we must first understand how the term has been defined and measured and practice. For a term like “interest,” which has varied colloquial and theoretical meanings, determining a definition from the literature is not straightforward. As a construct (i.e., an explanatory variable that is not directly observable), interest is complex. Motivational and learning theories have described interest as a multidimensional construct comprising affective (e.g., liking), cognitive (e.g., assigning value, storing knowledge), and behavioral (e.g., reengaging with specific content). No doubt the building students’ interest has a role to play in student performance. Interest has been valued as a key component of academic performance lack of interest course poor performance in students learning (Ainley & Hidi 2014).

In the discovery teaching strategy, the instructor guides the students to discover things by themselves, most of the activities in this teaching strategy was carried out by the learner. When students discovered things by themselves, knowledge gain retain and retrieved easily by the learners. Most of the concept in Biology require hand and mind in which discovery strategy help students to carried majority of the activities in learning concept.

The performance of students in Biology has reported been low, especially in Senior Secondary School Certificate Examination. The table below shows WAEC Chief Examiners report 2015b-2019

Year	No. of Students Registered	No. of Students Passed	No. of Students Failed	% Passed (A1-C6)	% Failed (D7-F9)
2015	50,926	23,900	27,026	46.93	53.07
2016	57,908	25,550	32,358	44.12	55.88
2017	59,567	27,056	32,511	45.42	54.58
2018	58,200	27,540	30,660	47.32	52.68
2019	66,020	30,965	35,055	46.90	53.10

Source: Kaduna State Quality Control Assurance Office (2019).

Table 1. Shows Biology students’ performance, consisting of percentage of students passed at credit level and percentage of those failed from 2015-2019 in Kaduna State. It’s clearly indicated that the students’ weaknesses in Biology as the percentage failure was higher than that of passes. this may not be unconnected with students’ poor performance in Ecology. Lack of using activity method of teaching such as discovery may be likely be the reason for the poor academic performance, interest among Biology students in learning ecology concept.

Adebanjo (2019). Adebanjo (2019) reported that most Biology teachers in secondary schools were using lecture method and this has consistently led to poor academic performance of the students especially in Biology. More so, Adebanjo (2019); Kurah (2019); Yusuf and Afolabi (2017) attributed lack of interest result poor performance in students. Therefore, the study investigated the Effect of Discovery Method on Interest in Ecology Concept among Senior Secondary School Students in Zaria Metropolis, Kaduna State

Objectives of the Study

The main objectives of this study are to determined:

1. The interest ability of SSII students’ taught ecology concept using discovery method and those taught same concept using conventional method.
2. If there is any difference in interest ability between male and female SSII students taught ecology concept using discovery method.

Research Questions

The study provided answers to the following research questions:

1. What is the difference in the mean interest scores of SSII students taught ecology Concept using discovery method and those taught the same concept using Conventional Method?

2. What is the difference in the mean interest scores of male and female SSII Students taught ecology concept using discovery method?

Research Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were formulated to guide the study and were tested at 0.05 level of significance.

1. There is no significant difference in the mean interest scores of SSII students taught Ecology concept using discovery method and those taught the same concept using Conventional method.
2. There is no significant difference in the mean interest scores of male and female SSII Students taught ecology concept using discovery method.

Methodology

The design for this study adopted quasi-experimental design involving pretest, posttest. The research design comprised of two schools in Zaria Education Zone. School N was used as experimental and school AD was used as control groups. The first week of the study was used for familiarity with school environment, teachers and students. Ecology Interest questionnaire as used in order to determine the equivalence in their ability level. Treatment was given to the experimental group by exposing the study subjects to Ecology Concepts using Discovery learning for Six weeks and control group was taught Ecology concepts with lecture method also for six weeks. At the end of six weeks treatment period, the post-test was administered to both groups (experimented and control).to determine the interest level of the students in ecology concepts.

The population of the study consists of 465 (Male,70 And Female,48) senior secondary school class two (SSII) Biology students during the 2023/2024 academic session among public schools in Zaria metropolis, Kaduna state, a sample size of 118 (70 male and 48 female) students were selected from the target population using multi-stage sampling technique.

The sample size was consisting of two schools, School N with sixty-five (65) students was assigned as experimental group, out of which thirty-eight (38) are male students and twenty-seven (27) female students while school AD with fifty-three (53) students was assigned as the control group, out of which thirty-two (32) students male and twenty-one (21) female students. A total of one hundred and eighteen (118) participants were used for the study out of which seventy (70) are males and forty eight (48) are females.

Table 2: Sample of the Study

S/N	Name of School	Male	Female	Total
1	School N (Experimental Group)	38	27	65
2	School AD (Control Group)	32	21	53
	Total	70	48	118

The study used simple random sampling technique to select two schools out of the Thirty-one (31) schools in Zaria Educational Zone, via balloting method. School N and School AD were randomly selected from the list as experimental group and control group respectively.

The Ecology Interest Questionnaire (EIQ) was adapted from Ahmad (2012), which was also used to measure students' interest in ecology. The EIQ includes a 5-point Likert scale with the following options: Strongly Agree (SA), Agree (A), Undecided (U), Disagree (A), and Strongly Disagree (SD). The items received respective scores of 5,4,3,2, and 1.

Model of discovery method used in this study was adapted from Mahmud (2016) comprised of five phases as illustrated in Fig. 1

Fig. 2.1: Phase Model of Discovery Teaching Method/Strategy Adapted from Abdurrahman (2016).

Result

The descriptive statistics (Mean and Standard Deviation) were used to answer the research questions and inferential (One-Way Analysis of Covariance, ANCOVA) statistical tools. All the research questions were answered using mean and standard deviation and all the hypotheses were tested using ANCOVA at $p \leq .05$ level of significance.

Research Question One: What is the difference in the mean interest scores of SSII students taught ecology Concept using discovery method and those taught the same concept using Conventional Method?

Table 3: Mean interest Scores of Students in Ecology.

Group	N	Mean (X)	S.D	M.D	Std Error Mean
Control	53	46.87	7.80	6.27	1.07
Experimental	65	53.14	8.63		1.07

From table 4.10 the students taught using conventional method of teaching has the mean interest score of 46.87 and the standard deviation of 7.80, while those exposed to discovery method has the mean score of 53.14 and the standard deviation of 8.63. The mean difference between the groups is 6.27, so this clearly shows that those taught using discovery method have high mean interest scores than those using conventional method.

Hypothesis One: There is no significant difference in the mean interest scores of SSII students taught Ecology concept using discovery method and those taught the same concept using Lecture method.

Table 4: ANCOVA analyses of post-post test mean interest Scores of Students in Ecology.

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Partial Eta Squared
Corrected Model	1153.985 ^a	2	576.993	8.372	.000	.127
Intercept	10377.043	1	10377.043	150.567	.000	.567
Pretest interest	6.052	1	6.052	.088	.768	.001
Group	1148.542	1	1148.542	16.665	.000	.127
Error	7925.778	115	68.920			
Total	307892.000	118				
Corrected Total	9079.763	117				

a. R Squared = .127 (Adjusted R Squared = .112)

Table 5 reveals the ANCOVA analyses for post-test mean interest scores of control and experimental groups, the F calculated value variable (interest) is 16.665 with the significant F at 0.000 which is less than 0.05 therefore, the null hypothesis is hereby rejected because the observed p-value is less than the significant level p-value (0.05). Hence, there is significant difference between the mean interest scores of secondary school Biology students taught using discovery method and those taught using lecture method of teaching, in favour of experimental group (f-cal = 16.665, p=0.000<0.05).

Research Question Two: What is the difference in the mean interest scores of male and female SSII Students taught ecology concept using discovery method?

Table 5: Mean interest of Male and Female Students in Ecology.

Group	N	Mean (X)	S.D	M.D	Std Error Mean
Male	38	50.76	9.41		1.52
Female	27	56.48	6.14	5.72	1.18

Table 6 indicated the mean interest scores of male and female students taught using discovery method, where male interest score is 50.76, with standard deviation of 9.41, while the female students' mean score is 56.48 and standard deviation of 6.14. The mean difference between the two groups is 5.72 in favour of female students which indicated that female students have high interest in Ecology when taught using discovery method of teaching than their male counter-part.

Hypothesis Two: There is no significant difference in the mean interest scores of male and female SSII Students taught ecology concept using discovery method.

Table 6: ANCOVA analyses of posttest mean interest Male and Female Students in Ecology.

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Partial Eta Squared
Corrected Model	516.158 ^a	2	258.079	3.762	.029	.108
Intercept	6677.623	1	6677.623	97.332	.000	.611
Pretest_int_exp	.014	1	.014	.000	.989	.000
Gender	513.130	1	513.130	7.479	.008	.108
Error	4253.595	62	68.606			
Total	188310.000	65				
Corrected Total	4769.754	64				

a. R Squared = .108 (Adjusted R Squared = .079)

Table 7 reveals the ANCOVA analyses for post-test mean interest scores of male and female Biology students taught ecology using discovery method of teaching, the F calculated value variable (interest) is 7.479 with the significant F at 0.008 which is less than 0.05 therefore, the null hypothesis is hereby rejected because the observed p-value is less than the significant

level p-value (0.05). Hence, there is significant difference in the mean interest scores of male and Female SSII students taught ecology using discovery method. ($f\text{-cal} = 7.479, p=0.008<0.05$).

1. There is significant difference in the mean interest scores of the SSII students taught ecology concept using discovery method and those taught that same concept using conventional method of teaching in favour of experimental group.
2. There is significant difference in the mean interest scores of male and female SSII students taught ecology concept using discovery method in favour of female.

Discussion of Findings

The results in table 4 shows the posttest mean interest scores of students taught with Discovery Method That is Experimental Group is higher than the posttest mean interest scores of students taught with conventional teaching method that is Control Group. However, the result in table 5 confirmed that the interest scores of experimental and control groups differs significantly. The result revealed that treatment using Discovery Method produced significant difference on students' interest in ecological concepts. Moreover, the current study indicated significant difference in the mean interest scores of SSII students taught Ecology concept using discovery method and those taught the same concept using Conventional method. This findings is in similar with the findings of Casad and Jawaharlal (2012) and Amiyani and Widjajanti (2018) who in their separate studies reported the effectiveness of guided discovery instructional strategy in improving students' interest. Also, the finding is in line of Yang (2009) who studied students from seven countries and found those who have both confidence and interest in learning science always showed positive achievements in the area of science. In contrast, Eccles, Fredricks & Epstein (2015) in their separate studies discovered no significant improvement in students' attitude and interest in Sciences, Social Sciences and Humanities among students under treatment. The study also found significant difference in the mean interest scores of male and female SSII Students taught ecology concept using discovery method. The results in table 6 show the posttest mean interest scores of male and female secondary school biology students taught ecological concepts using discovery method. The mean interest scores of the female students taught with mind mapping approach is higher than that of the male students taught with the same mind mapping approach. This indicated that the female students' interest scores differ significantly from the male interest scores. This is further confirmed by the result in table 7 which indicated that treatment using discovery method produced significant difference on gender. This finding is supported by [Renninger and Hidi, \(2015\)](#) which established significant differences between the interest of male and female students in Biology. On the contrary, the finding of Sofiani Maulida, Fadhillah and Sihite (2017) reported that gender's influence on students' interests to science was not significant.

Conclusion

The following conclusions were made based on the findings of this study. The result of this study provides empirical evidence that the use of discovery Method improves students' interest in ecological concepts more than the use of conventional teaching method. Furthermore, the study revealed

1. There is significant difference in the mean interest scores of the SSII students taught ecology concept using discovery method and those taught that same concept using conventional method of teaching in favour of experimental group.
2. There is significant difference in the mean interest scores of male and female SSII students taught ecology concept using discovery method in favour of female.

Recommendation

- i. Biology teachers should use discovery method of approach while teaching ecology so as to improve students' interest during the teaching and learning procedure.
- ii. Biology teachers should try as much as possible to guide their students in the interest on ecology concepts and how it influences their academic achievements.
- iii. The Biology teachers should try to carry along all the students during lessons irrespective of their gender.
- iv. Biology teachers should be encouraged to switch from lecture teaching methods to Discovery Method

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